

Theme: Building Water, Sanitation and Hygiene Resilience: Insights from the COVID-19 Pandemic WASH Debate Report-22nd March 2024 World Water Day.

Public Health Aid Awareness & Education Org (PHAAE)

The Webinar facilitated a dynamic exchange of ideas among professionals from diverse fields, including healthcare, WASH, engineering, climate experts, etc. The primary objective is to delve into crucial topics related to the lessons learned from the Covid 19 pandemic.

Some of the key topics that were discussed are:

- Addressing issues of corruption and mismanagement in the COVID response ; water and protective equipment distribution
- Mitigating infectious diseases through improved WASH Practices.
- Involving communities in WASH planning and implementation while strengthening community resilience through education.
- The impact of climate change on water sources and sanitation

PHAAE WASH DEBATE: WORLD WATER DAY 2024

Friday 22nd March 2024, 3:00pm-4:30pm

This is the summary of the key points from the webinar, PHAAE WASH Debate, in collaboration with experts.

Summary of Actions

Topics	Lead
Addressing issues of corruption and mismanagement in the COVID response water and protective equipment distribution	CESPAD
Mitigating infectious diseases through improved WASH Practices.	Keck School of Medicine, USC
Involving communities in WASH planning and implementation while strengthening community resilience through education	Fix It Engineering
The impact of climate change on water sources and sanitation	LOUD Climate Action
Next Webinar is scheduled to hold in 1 st May 2024. Agenda and meeting invitation will be circulated.	PHAAE
Moderator/Chair	City of York Council

1. Welcome

The Chair (Mike Southcombe) welcomed all the participating organization representatives, all the speakers and all present. He introduced the Host organization (PHAAE) and he introduced the first speaker.

2. The impact of climate change on water sources and sanitation: Rifkatu Odeyemi Joseph

- Water scarcity and quality: climate change alters precipitation patterns leading to more frequent and intense droughts in some regions and increased rainfall in others. These changes can disrupt water availability and quality.
- Impact on sanitation infrastructure: climate related extreme weather events, including hurricanes, flooding can damage sanitation infrastructure such as sewage treatment plants and septic systems leading to disruption in waste disposal.
- Economic and social impacts: Water scarcity and poor sanitation increase healthcare costs due to the burden of water borne diseases and related illnesses.
- Climate-induced environmental changes, such as sea-level rise and desertification, can force communities to migrate in search of water and sanitation resources. Displacement increases pressure on existing infrastructure in host communities and can exacerbate social tensions and health disparities, particularly for vulnerable populations such as refugees and internally displaced persons.

Discussion

The Chair invited questions for Ms Rifkatu

And he introduced the second speaker.

3. Involving communities in WASH planning and implementation while strengthening community resilience through education (Mr Prince Mekwunye Kidochukwu)

- Engaging communities in participatory needs assessments helps identify local priorities, challenges, and opportunities related to water and sanitation. By involving community members in data collection and analysis, WASH interventions can be tailored to meet the specific needs and preferences of the community, increasing their ownership and commitment to the project.
- Communities often possess valuable traditional knowledge and practices related to water management and sanitation. By integrating local knowledge into WASH planning and education initiatives, communities can leverage existing resources and practices to adapt to changing environmental conditions.
- Empowering community leaders and traditional authorities as advocates for WASH can enhance the acceptance and sustainability of interventions.
- Providing education and training on WASH practices, hygiene promotion, and climate resilience empowers community members to adopt and maintain healthy behaviors, such as handwashing, safe water storage, and sanitation practices.

- Education initiatives can target diverse audiences, including women, children, and vulnerable groups, to ensure equitable access to information and resources.
- Engaging communities in the design, construction, and maintenance of WASH infrastructure promotes ownership, accountability, and sustainability.
- Community-led approaches, such as the formation of water user committees or sanitation groups, enable communities to manage and maintain WASH facilities, monitor water quality, and respond to emerging challenges.
- WASH planning and education initiatives allow community members to collaborate, share experiences, and build social networks.
- Strengthening social cohesion fosters collective action and mutual support, enhancing community resilience to climate-related shocks and stresses.
- Community-based organizations and local institutions can serve as platforms for knowledge exchange, advocacy, and resource mobilization.

Discussion

The Chair invited questions for Mr Prince in the chat box. And he introduced the 3rd speaker.

4. Mitigating infectious diseases through improved WASH Practices (Neha Nanda MD)

- Ensuring access to safe and reliable water sources is essential for preventing waterborne diseases such as cholera, typhoid fever, and hepatitis A.
- Improved water sources, such as piped water systems, protected wells, and treated surface water, reduce the risk of waterborne pathogens contaminating drinking water supplies. Implementing water quality monitoring and treatment measures, such as chlorination and filtration, further enhances the safety of drinking water and prevents waterborne illnesses.
- Providing access to adequate sanitation facilities, such as toilets, latrines, and sewage systems, reduces the spread of fecal-oral pathogens and vector-borne diseases.
- Proper sanitation facilities prevent human waste from contaminating the environment and water sources, thereby minimizing the risk of diarrheal diseases, intestinal worms, and other infections. Effective waste management practices, including safe disposal of solid and liquid waste, further reduce environmental contamination and disease transmission.
- Promoting good hygiene practices, such as hand washing with soap, proper sanitation, and safe food handling, is critical for preventing the transmission of infectious diseases. Hygiene

education initiatives raise awareness about the importance of hand hygiene and encourage individuals to adopt hygienic behaviors in daily life. By incorporating hygiene promotion into community outreach programs, schools, and healthcare facilities, we can empower individuals to protect themselves and others from infectious diseases

Discussion

The chair called for questions for Dr Nanda and ushered in the last speaker.

5. Addressing issues of corruption and mismanagement in the COVID response water and protective equipment distribution: Ashah Shabaan

- The transparent processes for procurement, distribution, and monitoring of water and protective equipment.
- Published detailed information on budgets, expenditures, and allocations to promote accountability and public scrutiny.
- Implement mechanisms for independent oversight and regular audits to detect and deter corruption and mismanagement effectively.
- Leverage technology and innovation to enhance transparency, efficiency, and accountability in the distribution of water and protective equipment.
- Implement electronic procurement systems, blockchain technology, and digital tracking mechanisms to monitor the flow of resources, prevent diversion, and ensure real-time reporting and oversight.
- Explore innovative solutions, such as mobile applications and crowdsourcing platforms, to engage citizens in monitoring and reporting corruption risks.

AOB

Discussed the possibility of another pandemic sometime in the future and the preparedness of the WASH sector in Nigeria.

Attending Organizations

PHAAE (Host)

Water Integrity Networks

City of York Council

University of Southern California

HEKSEPER.ORG

UN Volunteers

LOUD Climate Action

UK Health Data Research Alliance

FEMinWASH Nigeria

Fix IT Nigeria Ltd

CESPAD

SAM Empowerment Foundation

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